

**Synthesis and Biological Activity of some
10-[3'-(1-Unsubstituted/Substituted-anilino-
malonyl-5'-phenyl)pyrazolinyl]phenothiazines
and 4-[3'-(1'-Unsubstituted/Substituted-
anilomalonyl-5'-phenyl)pyrazo-
linyl]morpholines**

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CHEMISTRY of pyrazolines, morpholines and phenothiazines have been extensively studied on account of their wide spectrum of biological activities¹. In view of the antimicrobial activities displayed by them and also by malonanilic acid hydrazides, a number of title compounds have been synthesised which combine structural features of these moieties.

N-Cinnamoylphenothiazine (**1**) was prepared by reacting phenothiazine with cinnamoyl chloride. Condensation of **1** with malonanilic acid hydrazides (**2**)² in dioxan/acetic acid furnished 10-[3'-(1'-unsubstituted/substituted-anilomalonyl-5'-phenyl)pyrazolinyl]phenothiazines (**3**) (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

4-[3'-(1'-Unsubstituted/substituted-5'-phenyl)pyrazolinyl]morpholines (**4**) were synthesised similarly using morpholine in place of phenothiazine.

Biological activities: Potentialities of five products **3b**, **3f**, **3j**, **4a** and **4h** have been assessed under disease-oriented *in vitro* human tumor cell line screen under AIDS screening programme. The response of **3b**, **3f**, **3j** was poor (2.80, 6.70 and 7.7% respectively), whereas **4a** and **4h** showed good acti-

vity of 39.40 and 61.60% on infected plates, whereas the response of others was poor.

Antimicrobial activity of compounds **3a**, **3d**, **3g**, **3j**, **4a** and **4h** was carried out using cup-plate method against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* and none showed significant activity in alcoholic solution at a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

Antifungal activity of **3h** was determined at a concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. Growth of *T. mentagrophytes* and *M. gypseum* was completely inhibited, while growth inhibition in case of *Candida albicans* was not significant. Products **4a** and **4d** could not check the growth of *C. albicans*, *Cryptococcus neoformans*, *Sporotrichum schenkii* and *Aspergillus fungigatus* in alcoholic solution at a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Purity was checked by tlc. All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses. The ir spectra (KBr) of phenothiazine derivatives (**3**) gave characteristic bands at 3 200–2 850 (CH), 1 650 (amide C=O), 750 (monosubstituted benzene) and 660 cm^{-1} (C–S–C). The morpholines (**4**) gave characteristic ir bands at 3 020, 3 110, 3 210 (CH), 1 620 (NH bend), 1 580, 1 480 (C=C) and 775 cm^{-1} (monosubstituted benzene).

10-[3'-(1'-Anilomalonyl-5'-phenyl)pyrazolinyl]phenothiazine: A mixture of cinnamoyl chloride (3.5 g, 0.02 mol) in dioxan (2 ml), triethylamine (2.1 g, 0.02 mol) and phenothiazine (4.0 g, 0.02 mol) was refluxed for 2 h and then left overnight. The resulting *N*-cinnamoylphenothiazine was recrystallised from ethanol as yellowish green crystals, (95%), m.p. 139° (Found: C, 77.60; H, 4.75; N, 4.19. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{16}\text{NOS}$ calcd. for: C, 76.59; H, 4.56; N, 4.25%).

A mixture of the above *N*-cinnamoylphenothiazine (0.001 mol), malonanilic acid hydrazide (0.001 mol), dioxan (1.0 ml) and glacial acetic acid (2 drops) was refluxed for 5 h and then cooled. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol.

4-[3'-(1'-Anilomalonyl-5'-phenyl)pyrazolinyl]morpholines: A mixture of cinnamoyl chloride (3.5 g, 0.02 mol) in dioxan (2.0 ml), morpholine (1.68 g, 0.02 mol) and triethylamine (2.1 g, 0.02 mol) was refluxed for 4 h and then left overnight. The resulting solid was purified by successive washing with hot dioxan, ether and acetone to yield white crystals, (46.94%), m.p. 169° (Found: C, 73.1; H, 5.2; N, 7.0. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{NO}$ calcd. for: C, 73.2; H, 5.16; N, 6.57%).

An intimate mixture of the above *N*-cinnamoylphenothiazine (0.001 mol) and malonanilic acid hydrazide (0.001 mol) was dissolved in dioxan (2 ml). A drop of trifluoroacetic acid was then added and contents were refluxed for 5 h and then cooled. The

resulting solid was purified by washing successively with boiling ethanol and hot dimethylformamide (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3 AND 4

Compd. no.	R	Mol. formula	M p. °C	Yield %
3a	H	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	288	44
3b	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	C ₃₁ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	272	32
3c	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	C ₃₁ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	271	31
3d	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₃₁ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	279	56
3e	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	C ₃₁ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₃ S	274	27.7
3f	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	C ₃₁ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₃ S	258	44.4
3g	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	C ₃₁ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₃ S	241	46.8
3h	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₃₀ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	274	14.6
3i	<i>m</i> -Cl	C ₃₀ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	265	18.6
3j	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₃₀ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	262	27.9
4a	H	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₃	245	38.56
4b	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₃	250d	37.22
4c	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₃	260d	29.77
4d	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₃	265	29.77
4e	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₄	248	50.11
4f	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ ClN ₄ O ₃	255	28.36
4g	<i>m</i> -Cl	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ ClN ₄ O ₃	261	23.64
4h	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ ClN ₄ O ₃	225	30.76

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

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References

1. A. N. KOST, G. N. PERSHIN, V. V. ERSHOV, S. N. MILOVANOVA and E. B. EVREINOVA, *Sov. Mat. Mekhan. Ashvin, Fiz F. I. Khim.*, 1959, **14**, 211; G. D. THORN, *Phytopathology*, 1961, **51**, 77; R. ANDRISANI, L. CHUVID and F. CRAVESI, *Arzneim-Forsch.*, 1958, **8**, 708; E. KREFFEL, *Arch Int. Pharmacodyn Therap*, 1957, **112**, 20
2. B. S. RAYHORE and P. I. ITTYERAH, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1960, **37**, 9.

Synthesis of some New 4-Hydrazido-1,4-benzoxazin-3(2H)-ones and their Triazolo Derivatives as Possible Antibacterial Agents

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It has been reported that some fused triazoles of 1,4-benzoxazin-3(2H)-ones possess promising pharmacological properties¹. The presence of halogen

atoms in benzene ring of benzoxazine molecule imparts marked antibacterial activity to 4-*N*-dialkylhydrazido derivatives^{2,3}. On the basis of these observations the synthesis of 4-hydrazido-1,4-benzoxazin-3(2H)-ones (3a-h)² was undertaken. On cyclodehydration with ammonium acetate and acetic acid these were converted to 5-oxo-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*c*]-2(H), 3(H)-1,4-benzoxazines 4 (Scheme 1).

- (a), R=R''=Br, R'=H (e), R=Br, R'=H, R''=CH₃
 (b), R=Br, R'=H, R''=Cl (f), R=R''=Br, R'=CH₃
 (c), R=Cl, R'=H, R''=Br (g), R=CH₃, R'=H, R''=Br
 (d); R=R''=CH₃, R'=H (h), R=Cl, R'=CH₃, R''=Br

Scheme 1 Reagents: (i) Cl-COOC₂H₅/K₂CO₃/CH₃OH, (ii) N₂H₄·H₂O/C₂H₅OH, (iii) CH₃COOH/CH₃COONH₄.

All these compounds (3 and 4) were screened for their antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus aureus*, *Esch. coli* and *Salmonella typhosa* by the cup-plate method⁴ at concentration of 1 mg ml⁻¹ in acetone.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer R-237 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. 1,4-Benzoxazin-3(2H)-ones (1a-h) were prepared by the known procedure². For compounds 2-4, b and c have same not formulae, which is also true for the pair e and g. Elemental analysis for C, H and N, were found satisfactory for all compounds.

Preparation of 2a-h: A mixture of 1e (0.03 mol), ethyl chloroformate (0.07 mol) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (3.0 g) in methanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 5 h, cooled and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The solid obtained was triturated with water to remove K₂CO₃, filtered and crystallised from ethanol to give 2e (83%), m.p. 78° (Found: C, 45.80; H, 3.80; N, 4.40. C₁₂H₁₂O₄NBr requires: C, 46.01; H, 3.83; N, 4.47%); ν_{max} 1740 (C=O, ester), 1670 (C=O, δ -lactam) and 1320 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C); δ 1.3 (3H, t, J 7Hz, CH₃), 2.25 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 4.2 (2H, q, J 7Hz, CH₂), 4.6 (2H, s, OCH₂) and 6.6-7.5 (2H,